

Unlocking Microbiome Insights

Dr. Liz Mallott on the Power of Reusing Existing Data

Reusing diverse datasets, openly available on platforms like Figshare, was crucial for this meta-analysis project. Existing datasets provided the necessary geographic spread and a wide age range of participants to comprehensively investigate gut microbiome development across stages of early life.

Researchers	NIH funding
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Liz Mallott Professor, Departments of Biology and Entomology Director, One Health Microbiome Center Pennsylvania State University	<p>National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Microbiota and Allergic Asthma Precision Prevention (MAAP2) (P01AI089473) <p>National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Siblings Reared Apart: A Naturalistic Cross-Fostering Study of Young Children (R01DA035062) <p>National Institute of General Medical Sciences (NIGMS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Microbial Ecology and Theory of Animals Center for Excellence in Systems Biology (P50GM098911)• BUILD PODER II (RL5GM118975) <p>Office of the Director (OD)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Host genetics, early-life microbiome, and childhood asthma: MARC-43 Boston (UG3OD023253)• The Early Growth and Development Study Pediatric Cohort (UH3OD023389)
Figshare datasets reused	Related publication
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Herman, D. & Flores, G. (2019). Sequence and supplementary data for "Dietary habits of two to nine-year-old American children are associated with gut microbiome composition." <i>figshare</i>. 10.6084/m9.figshare.7011272• Cioffi, C. C., Tavalire, H. F., Neiderhiser, J. M., Bohannon, B., & Leve, L. D. (2020). History of breastfeeding but not mode of delivery shapes the gut microbiome in childhood. <i>PLOS ONE</i>. Collection. 10.1371/journal.pone.0235223	<p>Mallott, E. K., Sitarik, A. R., Leve, L. D., Cioffi, C., Camargo, C. A., Hasegawa, K., and Bordenstein, S. R. (2023). Human microbiome variation associated with race and ethnicity emerges as early as 3 months of age. <i>PLOS Biology</i> 21(8), e3002230. 10.1371/journal.pbio.3002230</p>
Other datasets reused	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• NCBI's Sequence Read Archive accessions PRJNA322554, PRJEB11697, and PRJEB13896• Qiita studies 11129 and 10894	

In an era where data sharing is becoming increasingly vital for scientific advancement, research conducted by [Dr. Liz Mallott](#), an assistant professor of biology at Washington University in St. Louis, is a prime example of

successful data reuse. Her work on the gut microbiome in children, conducted as a meta-analysis of existing datasets and published in [PLOS Biology](#) in 2023, highlights the power of collaborative science and open data practices.

SHORT REPORTS

Human microbiome variation associated with race and ethnicity emerges as early as 3 months of age

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Abstract

Human microbiome variation is linked to the incidence, prevalence, and mortality of many diseases and associates with race and ethnicity in the United States. However, the age at which microbiome variability emerges between these groups remains a central gap in knowledge. Here, we identify that gut microbiome variation associated with race and ethnicity arises after 3 months of age and persists through childhood. One-third of the bacterial taxa that vary across caregiver-identified racial categories in children are taxa reported to also vary between adults. Machine learning modeling of childhood microbiomes from 8 cohort studies (2,756 samples from 729 children) distinguishes racial and ethnic categories with 87% accuracy. Importantly, predictive genera are also among the top 30 most important taxa when childhood microbiomes are used to predict adult self-identified race and ethnicity. Our results highlight a critical developmental window at or shortly after 3 months of age when social and environmental factors drive race and ethnicity-associated microbiome variation and may contribute to adult health and health disparities.

Introduction

Two major goals of the human microbiome science include increasing the representation of undersampled groups in microbiome datasets [1–3] and understanding the tempo by which inequitable experiences, intergenerational inequality, and structural racism impact

Screenshot of published paper: Mallott, E. K., *et al.* (2023). Human microbiome variation associated with race and ethnicity emerges as early as 3 months of age. *PLoS Biology* 21(8), e3002230. [10.1371/journal.pbio.3002230](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3002230)

Unraveling the Gut Microbiome in Early Life

Dr. Mallott's research is focused on understanding the factors that shape gut microbiome variation in humans. Her postdoctoral work in [Dr. Seth Bordenstein's lab](#) at Vanderbilt University had observed a signal of race or ethnicity in adult gut microbiome variation, a puzzling finding given that race and ethnicity are social constructs and do not reflect inherent biological differences. To investigate the origins of this signal, Dr. Mallott's team decided to look at childhood data, hypothesizing that early life factors or social environmental determinants of health might be at play.

The project involved a meta-analysis of all available childhood gut microbiome data where investigators had inquired about race and ethnicity. Dr. Mallott focused her search on data

from the U.S. to ensure more standardized definitions of race and ethnicity, and ultimately pulled together data from eight different studies comprising a cumulative 2,756 gut microbiome samples from 729 U.S. children between birth and 12 years of age.

Key Findings: When the Signal Emerges

The meta-analysis revealed that race and ethnicity are not associated with the gut microbiome at birth or during the first three months of life. However, a signal begins to emerge between three and twelve months of age, indicating that something occurring at or after three months of age - likely one or more social or environmental factors - leads to differences in gut microbiome development in children. While the effect size is small, it is statistically significant.

The Power of Data Reuse: A Pandemic Project

One of the most striking aspects of Dr. Mallott's research is that it was based entirely on reused data; no new data was collected. This approach was particularly strategic, especially as it was undertaken during the pandemic when data collection was challenging. As Dr. Mallott explains, "It was a giant meta-analysis where we didn't collect any new data. I was actually doing this work during COVID, so it was nice not to have to go into a lab or recruit people. It worked really well." The project's reliance on existing datasets allowed for a wide geographic spread within the U.S., which was crucial for the study.

Navigating Data Access and Collaboration

Dr. Mallott's process for finding and accessing data was driven primarily by published literature. The ease of access varied: some datasets were readily available on platforms like the National Institutes of Health's [SRA \(Sequence Read Archive\)](#) or [dbGaP \(database of Genotypes and Phenotypes\)](#), while others required direct contact with the original researchers. Dr. Mallott noted that most

researchers were responsive and helpful.

A particularly positive experience involved working with a group of researchers that had shared data in Figshare. Their [collection](#) of figures and datasets was published to Figshare in support of an article in *PLOS ONE*:

Cioffi, C. C. *et al.* (2020). History of breastfeeding but not mode of delivery shapes the gut microbiome in childhood. *PLOS ONE*. [10.1371/journal.pone.0235223](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0235223).

The collection included figures and datasets supporting the figures, but due to the sensitive nature of this human subjects data, the raw data was not publicly shared. However, upon reaching out to the original researchers, Dr. Leslie Leve and Dr. Camille Cioffi at the University of Oregon, Dr. Mallott found them to be responsive and happy to help. They ultimately became co-authors on the *PLOS Biology* paper. Similar collaborations also formed with groups at Henry Ford Health System and Massachusetts General Hospital. This highlights how data reuse can foster new scientific collaborations.

Screenshot of figure in collection of reused data shared via PLOS ONE Figshare portal: Cioffi, C. C. *et al.* (2020). Relative abundance of the most common genera by

feeding practice. *PLOS ONE*. [10.1371/journal.pone.0235223.g002](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0235223.g002)

The project involved datasets spanning a wide age range, from birth through puberty, with a cutoff at 12 years. Drs. Leve & Cioffi's Figshare datasets, for instance, focused on children ages 3-18, while other datasets covered very early infancy. The diversity of datasets was essential for covering the full age spectrum needed for the analysis.

Overcoming Challenges: Data Standardization and Metadata

Reusing data from various sources collected over a 10-year period presented challenges, particularly in re-coding and standardizing the data. Differences in sequencing protocols, such as primer sets and platforms, also needed to be accounted for. Dr. Mallott emphasized the invaluable help from co-authors in consistently re-coding the data.

Regarding data sharing, Dr. Mallott's team shared all analysis code in the [Childhood micro analysis](#) GitHub repository and archived it on Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.8063023](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8063023)). While they could not re-share the raw data due to sensitive populations and controlled access requirements, they did share all processed data underlying the figures in the paper as supplementary material, available via the [PLOS Figshare portal](#). This commitment to sharing code and processed data contributes significantly to research reproducibility and transparency.

Evolving Landscape of Data Sharing in Microbiome Science

Throughout her career thus far, Dr. Mallott has observed a consistent expectation of robust data sharing within the microbiome sciences field. Influential projects like the American Gut Project (now the [Microsetta Institute](#)) and the [Human Microbiome Project](#) set a precedent for public data availability from their inception. For Dr. Mallott, it has more or less always been an expectation to make sequencing data publicly available through platforms like the National

Human microbiome variation associated with race and ethnicity emerges as early as 3 months of age

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Institutes of Health's SRA or dbGaP, especially for sensitive populations. She has also shared metabolomic data on [Figshare](#) and Dryad.

While the sharing of raw sequence data (FASTQ files) has been standardized for a long time, the evolution of metadata standards has been particularly interesting. Initially, metadata provision was more flexible, but platforms like SRA have become stricter with their requirements. Dr. Mallott noted a slow evolution of metadata standards in the field, with recommended standards like MiMARKS (minimum information about a marker gene sequence) already in use when she began her career. Recent years have seen a concerted

effort to codify expectations for sharing microbiome data, including the development of the Strengthening the Organization and Reporting of Microbiome Studies (STORMS) checklist for sample processing and the ongoing work by the [Microbiome Centers Consortium](#) to establish robust field-wide metadata standards.

Advice for Data Management and Reuse

Dr. Mallott offers practical advice for researchers, emphasizing the importance of proactive metadata management. She suggests establishing a metadata file at the beginning of a project, including all required and desired information, and filling it out as the analysis progresses. This practice makes data sharing a less arduous task down the line. From the perspective of a data re-user, comprehensive metadata is highly valued, although she acknowledges it's not always feasible, especially with sensitive human or endangered species data. Finally, Dr. Mallott advises researchers not to hesitate to reach out to the authors of a paper if data isn't fully public or clear. As she explains, "Most people are very helpful and willing to share the data as long as they know that it's going to be used in a careful manner." Such outreach, she notes, can even lead to fruitful collaborations.

Dr. Mallott's experience underscores the immense value of data sharing and reuse in accelerating scientific discovery and fostering collaboration within the research community.

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